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REVIEW ON FLUDIZED BED GRANULATION AND COATING USING FLUDIZED BED COATER

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ABSTRACT

Formulation development is the most emerging and upcoming face of pharmaceutical technology in the current era. The day-to-day advancements in the research have provided an edge to this brilliant branch of pharmaceutical sector for not only uplifting the pharmacy profession but also to conquer the diseased state for nurturing the health and humanity. The fluid-bed technology or air-suspension process is the potential tool to develop newer trends and implications in the sector of formulation development with maximum therapeutic efficacy. Fluid bed granulation is a key pharmaceutical process which improves many of the powder properties for tablet compression. Granules of high quality can be obtained by understanding and controlling the critical process parameters by timely measurements. The technology is used for granulation/agglomeration, layering and coating of a wide range of particle size. In addition; the technique can be used for the drying process as well. The three patterns of the fluid-bed processes could be characterized by the position/location of the spray nozzle i.e. top spray, bottom spray or tangential spray. These advanced pelletizing technologies are recently added to complement the actual capabilities of standard fluid bed processing for development of various dosage forms of "Multiple Unit Particulate Systems" (MUPS) with better therapeutic efficacy and economic benefits. The aim of this review is to review some of the general aspect of fluid bed granulation & some common techniques which are utilized in pharmaceutical industry.

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INTRODUCTION:[1-5,41]**Historical development**

In 1922, Fritz Winkler made the first industrial application of fluidization in a reactor for a coal gasification process. In 1942, the first circulating fluid bed was built for catalytic cracking of mineral oils, with fluidization technology applied to metallurgical processing (roasting arsenopyrite) in the late 1940s. During this time theoretical and experimental research improved the design of the fluidized bed. In the 1960s VAW-Lippewerk in Lünen, Germany implemented the first industrial bed for the combustion of coal and later for the calcination of aluminium hydroxide.

Concept of fluidization:

The fluidized bed shows the following properties:

- Lighter objects float on top of the bed
- The solids can flow through an opening in the vessel
- The beds have a static pressure head due to gravity.
- It has a zero angle of repose

PRINCIPLE OF FLUIDIZATION: [1-3]

The principle of fluidization is that, when a gas is sent through a nozzle with a velocity greater than the settling velocity of particles or solids, the particles tend to suspend in the air provided and continue in the stream of upward gas. When the particles reach the top of the equipment, they tend to gravitational pull and so fall down and this process of suspending continues. This process is called as fluidization of suspended particles (Ylirussi, 2004; Vuppala, 1997).

Theory of fluidization: [3,9]

The following are the stages of fluidization:

- a) Static bed
- b) Expanded bed
- c) Mobile bed
- d) Bubble formation
- e) Pneumatic transport

Static bed:

When the velocity of the suspending air is low, the supplied air passes through the void spaces of the bed without disturbing the particles by which no air suspension of particles takes place.

Expanded bed:

At an intermediate flow rate of the air used, the bed gets expanded in the stream, this is called as expanded bed.

Mobile bed:

When the flow of air stream is very high i.e., with high velocity, the particulate bed is swept off to the top of the vessel. This is called as mobile bed.

Bubble formation:

When the velocity increases, the bed expands and bubble formation occurs.

Pneumatic transport:

This occurs when the air velocity further increases leading to the blowing of the particles out of the stream.

Figure.1.Stages of Fluidization.

Applications of Fluid bed processing (Gu, 2004; Banks, 1991; Kristensen, 2000):

Drying:[4]

Fluid bed drying is an especially effective way of drying solids. During fluidization, liquid is withdrawn from the entire surface of every single particle. The advantages are excellent heat exchange, ideal drying time.

Drying.

Granulation/ agglomeration:[5]

Agglomeration in the fluid bed is a modern method of creating granulates from powder disusing liquid bridges. The sprayed liquid can be either water or an organic solvent or another binder. The moist granulates are dried or cooled. As a result, the agglomerates are loose, have a low bulk density and are outstandingly soluble in water.

Granulation.

Powder coating / Particle coating:[6]

Modern film coating selectively influences the product characteristics through the application of protective films. A very uniform application of the coating material is important during coating. The coating must provide an absolute seal without mechanical damage or tears. Film coating is a technically demanding process that can be used over a very wide spectrum.

Powder coating.**Pelletizing:[7,8]**

During pelletizing, powder is mixed and moistened. At the same time, a solvent or binding agent can be added. The centrifugal motion produces agglomerates which are spheronized into uniform, dense pellets. Selective product characteristics can be realized through direct pelletizing or layering.

Pelletizing

Granulation is an important application in the agrochemical, pharmaceutical, food and mining industries to convert small diameter particles into large diameter agglomerates made up of initial particles.

Concept of granulation :[41]

Granulation is the act or process of forming into grains or granules.^[1] Granules typically have a size range between 0.2 and 4.0 mm depending on their subsequent use.

Principle of Granulation

The powder is fluidized by the hot air in fluid bed granulator. The binding liquid such as solution, suspension is sprayed on the fluidized powder to build liquid bridges among them to form agglomerates.

The liquid bridge that serve to hold the particle together in two ways,

- 1) by surface tension at the air liquid interface
- 2) by hydrostatic suction.

The liquid bridges are dried by the hot fluid air to stick the powder together. While the liquid sprayed continuously, the particles grow bigger to a desire granule size. The process is carried out continuously. Finally it forms ideal, uniform and porous granules.

Purposed of granulation :[42]

Granulation is carried out for various reasons, one of which is to prevent the segregation of the constituents of powder mix. Segregation is due to differences in the size or density of the component of the mix.

Normally, the smaller and/or denser particles tend to concentrate at the base of the container with the larger and/or less dense ones on the top. An ideal granulation will contain all the constituents of the mix in the correct proportion in each granule and segregation of granules will not occur.

Many powders, because of their small size, irregular shape or surface characteristics, are cohesive and do not flow well. Granules produced from such a cohesive system will be larger and more isodiametric, both factors contributing to improved flow properties.

Some powders are difficult to compact even if a readily compactable adhesive is included in the mix, but granules of the same powders are often more easily compacted. This is associated with the distribution of the adhesive within the granule and is a function of the method employed to produce the granule.

Process of the granulation:[18]

In the pharmaceutical industry, wet and dry granulation are most common processes employed in the production of solid dosage forms, although in certain situations, direct blending is also possible. Given the importance of granulation in the production of oral dosage forms and the technique's extensive use in the industry, it's essential to understand the principles and options, which are summarised below.

Dry Granulation:[42]

This process is used to form granules without using a liquid solution, because the product to be granulated may be sensitive to moisture (an ideal way to process compounds that are physically or chemically unstable when exposed to moisture) and heat. Forming granules without moisture involves compacting and size reduction of the mix to produce a granular, free flowing blend of uniform size. Dry granulation can be done in two ways: either a large tablet (slug) is produced in a heavy duty tableting press or the powder is squeezed between two rollers to produce a sheet of materials (roller compactor/chilsonator). When a tablet press is used for dry granulation, the powders may not possess enough natural flow to feed the product uniformly into the die cavity, resulting in varying degrees of densification. The roller compactor (granulator-compactor) uses an auger-feed system that will consistently deliver powder uniformly between two pressure rollers. When the product is compacted properly, it can then be passed through a mill and final blend before tablet compression.

Wet Granulation:[42]

The process of wet granulation involves the addition of a liquid solution to the powder mixture and the massing of the mix to produce granules. The fluid contains a solvent that must be evaporated, so that it can be removed by drying. Typical liquids include water, ethanol and isopropanol, either alone or in combination. Once the powders have formed into a dense mass and the granulation fluid has been evaporated then the granules are milled to an appropriate size for compression. The process can be very simple or very complex depending on the characteristics of the powders and the final dosage form. Organic solvents are used when water-sensitive drugs are processed, as an alternative to dry granulation, or when a rapid drying time is required. Because direct compression is not the best technology for many active substances, wet granulation is still a preferred method. Even if the active substance is sensitive to hydrolysis, modern equipment (a fluidized bed, for example) eliminates the problems associated with wet granulation.

Concept of coating :[9]

The coating of particles is practiced in various industries for several reasons. For pharmaceuticals, coatings are used

- 1) To mask unpleasant tastes or odors
- 2) For product identification
- 3) To enhance stability (e.g., to act as a moisture barrier)
- 4) To modify or control drug release
- 5) To improve product flowability.

In general, there are two types of coating applications: film coating (using a wax, aqueous, latex, or organic coating system) and substrate layering. The latter produces pellets or spherical forms of a substrate by layering it, in powder or liquid form (e.g., solution, suspension, or emulsion), onto inert carriers such as sugar spheres. [17-18] the pellets are then coated for modified or controlled-release dosage forms. Common coating materials can be grouped into three categories: waxes, water-insoluble polymers, and water soluble polymers. Water-insoluble polymers can be applied via an organic solvent system or an aqueous system such as latex or pseudo latex dispersions. Because of environmental concerns regarding the use of organic solvents, aqueous dispersions have gained popularity. [17-20]

The coating of pharmaceutical products has been practiced for more than 1000 years (1).

The traditional reason for tablet coating was to mask unpleasant tastes and to improve the cosmetic appearance of the product.

More recently, the application of enteric and sustained-release coatings have increased the need to control more accurately the distribution of coating material on pharmaceutical products (2).

Coating

The most commonly known fluid-bed process for coating in the pharmaceutical industry is the bottom-spray (Wurster) process. Developed by Dr. Dale Wurster in the late 1950s, the technique is well recognized for providing excellent coating uniformity and efficiency.

The bottom-spray (Wurster) fluid-bed method is very popular in the pharmaceutical industry for active layering and for coating to modify or control drug release because it produces a superior film compared with other coating techniques.

Method

Fluid bed process ;[9]

Types of fluid bed processing systems:

1. Drying
2. Granulation
3. Coating

Types of FBP according to the position of the spray gun (Meshram, 2005; Vazquez, 1991; Lachman, 1991; Vertommen, 1997): [10]

- a) Top spray
- b) Bottom spray
- c) Tangential spray

Top spray:

This processing option is frequently used by the food, feed and chemical industries as the function of the film mainly serves to improve the general handling or storage time i.e., time limited protection against moisture, oxygen or light. A perfect film is generally not required for this function, but care must be taken that the droplets do not become too viscous before touching the substrate, in order to maintain a good spreadability.

Advantages of top spray:

Agglomeration or granulation processes:

- Reduction in the amount of fines
- Improvement in the flow
- Elimination of segregation
- Homogenous distribution of all components
- Controllable bulk density
- Optimized solubility

Coating process:

- Lipid coating, taste masking
- Moisture and oxidation protection coating
- Enteric coating

Bottom spray coating:[11,12]

This processing option uses the energies and controls of the fluid bed to create a pneumatic mass transport inside a special insert, which consists of a perforated bottom screen with defined free areas. Most of the process air is channelled through the centre via a tube as such producing a venturi effect, which sucks the product from outside the partition past the spray nozzle. Leaving the cylindrical partition and entering the conical expansion chamber. The particle velocity is dramatically reduced, excess moisture is rapidly evaporated with the dry product returning again and again through the coating zone to receive more coating material.

This uniform statistical residence time of all particles in the coating zone results in a very homogenous coating. Due to the nozzle being positioned directly inside the product and concurrently spraying a premature viscosity change of the coating droplet is avoided. All this features result in the highest possible coating quality, which is imperatively required to produce defined and reproducible drug delivery profiles.

The Wurster bottom spray method makes it possible to attain high- quality results in coating in coating pellets and particles. The combination of the nozzle positioned directly in the product bed and the controlled product motion made possible by the inner partitions results in an extremely quick and thus economical process.

Some of the advantages are:

- Aqueous or organic
- Polymer solutions or dispersions
- Controlled release
- Enteric coating
- Coating of very fine particles
- Active ingredient layering

Tangential spray:[13,14]

This processing technique is with its physical principles quite similar to bottom- spray coating, only that the production motion is provided by a motor driven rotor disc. Otherwise, the quality producing parameters are the same:

Uniform statistical residence time is warranted by defined rotor revolution speed. The coating material is sprayed concurrently inside the rotating product. The rolling motion of the particles provides an even higher separation force, as such preventing agglomeration. However, this high kinetic energy makes it somewhat difficult to coat very small particles and is generally destructive for larger and non- spherical products. The benefits of this processing option are mainly for the layering and subsequent film coating of pellets.

Uses of tangential spray: [15-17]**Granulation process:**

For improved dissolution behaviour, better compressibility, higher density, spherical morphology

Spheronization:

Higher density, production of pellets, higher content of active ingredients.

Layering:

Powder layering, narrow particle size distribution

Coating:

Film coating, enteric coating, delayed release and hot- melt coating.

Types of FBP according to the position of the spray gun.

Granulation processes :[18]

Granulation parameters:

Position of nozzle:

Based on the bed height, the position of nozzle should be adjusted, for better drying.

Spray rate:

Spray rate should be optimized for prevention of over granulation.

Spray pressure:

Pressure should be monitored continuously as the change in pressure leads to improper drying and granulation process

Fluidized bed granulator :[36]

Is one of the processing equipment that is commonly used in the pharmaceutical industries. It is a multi-purpose equipment in that mixing, granulation and drying are all carried out in the same equipment. Fluidized bed granulator normally operates in a bubbling bed regime.

The main parts of any fluidized bed granulator which may have different design options, following the direction of fluidization gas flow includes;

Gas plenum (Gas inlet chamber) which screws as the receiver for inlet fluidization air. Gas distribution. Product container. An expanded chamber containing a set of filter bag in the expansion chamber. Binders spray system which is usually characterized by one of four nozzle design.

Pressure nozzle –

This type of nozzle breaks up fluid under pressure by its inherent instability and its impact on the atmosphere, one another jet or on a fixed plate.

Rotating nozzle –

This nozzle type is also known as rotary atomizer and it is used mainly in spray drying application.

Airless spray nozzle –

With this type of nozzle, the fluid is separated into two streams that are brought back together at the nozzle orifice, where upon impingement forms drops.

Gas atomizing nozzle –

This is equally known as two-fluid nozzle. With this nozzle, the binder solution (one fluid) is atomized by compressed air (the second fluid). It is most commonly used nozzle for fluid bed granulation.

Different designs can be selected for individual main parts of a fluidized bed granulator and this depends on

1. Processing option.
2. Mode of operation (batch or continuous).
3. Use of equipment.

Principle of processing : [37,38]

Conventional fluidized bed granulator can be operated depending on the position of the spray system in either “top” for top-spray fluidized bed granulator or “bottom” for bottom spray fluidized bed granulator. □
Fluidized bed granulator in general is not different from industrial fluidized bed coating equipment except that the spraying zone occupies a large portion of the bed and also gas velocities used are somewhat similar. Granulation in a fluidized bed granulator is achieved by suspending the powder in the air of the fluidized bed and then spraying the binder solution from nozzles that are either positioned above or below the powder bed depending on the type of the granulator.

Advantages of Fluidized Bed Granulator : [39]

- Fluidized bed granulator is a one unit system and thus saves labour cost, transfer loss and time.
- Heat transfer in fluidized bed granulator is 2-6 times greater than that generated by tray dryer.
- The process can be automated once parameters are optimized. Drying occurs uniformly and the process prevents mottling.

Disadvantages of Fluidized Bed Granulator [40]

- It is practicable impossible to achieve the same degree of densification while using fluidized bed granulator in batch mode. The equipment is characterized by long resident time.
- There is need for relatively high amount of granulating liquid.
- Fluidized bed granulator is expensive to acquire.
- There is tendency of filter clogging, demising, electrostatic charge and solvent explosion is high. it also produces low-density granules.

Coating parameters: [19]**Distance of spray nozzle:**

Distance of spray nozzle plays an important role in deciding the coating process as the more distance leads to evaporation of the coating solution and the less distance leads to over wetting of the particles or the dosage forms.

Droplet size:

Droplet size is inversely proportional to the efficiency of coating. The lesser the droplet size, the more is the uniformity of coating of the solution.

Spray rate:

The spray rate should not be too fast or too slow. Optimum spray rate is to be maintained for better coating to take place.

Spray pressure:

Atomization of coating solution depends on the spray pressure.

Moisture in the equipment leads to degradation of hygroscopic substances. Coating solution is to be dried well so that uniform coating occurs. So, the temperature should also be monitored for a better coating solution.

Time of drying also plays a major role in coating process. If the time of drying increases, the coating layer may get brittle and leads to processing problems and if the coating layer is not well dried, the doublets and the triplets are formed due to the sticking of the tablets to one another. The coating solution is to be selected based upon the parameters used. If the coating solution is an organic solution, it may catch fire due to the high temperature inlet air used. During a coating process, the opposite nature materials is to be used. i.e., when hydrophilic material is used as starting material, the hydrophobic material is to be used as coating material and vice versa.

The three patterns of the fluid-bed processes could be characterized by the position/location of the spray nozzle i.e. top spray, spray and tangential spray.^[20,21,22]

Table 1: Parts of fluid bed coating machine parts of fluid bed coating machine

Parts of Fluid Bed Coating Machine		
1	Nozzle	Droplet size and Distribution is controlled
2	ADP	Distribute fluidizing air between the inner and outer partitions
3	Plenum	Chamber Equalise pressure for more even distribution
4	Cylinder(pG)	Particles are actually sucked through the partition gap
5	Candles/ Filter bags	For continuous fluidization
6	Expansion chamber	For recurring flow of the particles

Process variables for the Fluid bed coating technology include the liquid addition rate, inlet air temperature, fluidization blower speed, process air humidity, and the atomization air pressure. It should be noted that atomization air volume is the key variable, but it often is gauged by atomization air pressure. [21,26]

Table 2: Process Parameters and Formulation Parameters in Fluid Bed Coating Parameters Process.

Parameters	
Process Parameters	
1	Blower speed
2	Atomization
3	Inlet temperature
4	Spray rate
5	Pump rpm
Formulation Parameters	
1	Strength of coating solution
2	Size distribution of substrate
3	Batch size of substrate

Fluid Bed Coating Process**FBC Operation and Operation Parameters:[23]**

Air enters through the plenum chamber and is evenly distributed to provide uniform fluidization and heat transfer. Pellets are fluidized by air stream, as the particle moves upward, they are decelerated in the expansion chamber and then fall outside the wurster column. The returned particles move downward until they are sucked back up to the loop again. Pellets are actually sucked through the gap, drawn to the centre of the plate, and accelerated inside of the partition (re-enter the partition column through the partition gap) and repeat the fountain-like cyclic flow. Particles receive coating droplets during the passage through the spray zone and dried by hot air within the partition column.

Critical Quality Risk Analysis of CPPs by QRM:

Risk assessment is a valuable science-based process used in Quality Risk Management (QRM) (ICH Q9) that aided in identifying which material attributes and process parameters potentially had an effect on product Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs). Risk assessment is typically performed early in the development stage & is repeated as more information & greater knowledge is obtained. Risk assessment tools i.e. matrix analysis & Failure Mode Effective Analysis (FMEA) can be concisely used to identify and rank parameters with potential to have an impact on IP/FP CQAs, based on prior knowledge and initial experimental data. Risk analysis is the estimation of the risk associated with the identified hazards. It is the qualitative or quantitative process of linking the likelihood of occurrence and severity of harms.

Critical Quality Risk Analysis of Process Parameters of Fluid Bed Coating Technology:

Ability to detect the harm (detectability) also factors in the estimation of risk. Risk evaluation compares the identified and analyzed risk against given risk criteria. This list can be refined further through experimentation to determine the significance of individual variables and potential interactions through a combination of DOEs, mathematical models or studies that lead to mechanistic understanding to achieve a higher level of process understanding.

Method for coating:[24,25]**Quality Risk Analysis**

Recent regulatory guidelines strongly encourage the pharmaceutical industry to apply scientific and risk. Management approaches to the development of a product and its manufacturing process. Qualitative Initial Risk-Assessment from prior knowledge and Quantitative Failure Mode Effective Analysis (FMEA) are used to identify and rank parameters with potential to have an impact on in Process/Finished Product Critical Quality Attributes (IP/FP CQAs). These Critical. Process Parameters (CPPs) were further refined by DoE that leads to implementation of a control strategy to achieve consistent finished product quality to prevent possible product failure.

Figure: Shows Diagrammatic Representation of Quality Risk Management Process.

Risk assessment consists of the identification of hazards and the analysis and evaluation of risks associated with exposure to those hazards. Quality risk assessments begin with a well-defined problem description or risk question

Design of Experiment:[27,28]

From the above Pareto analysis, the most three critical process parameters in fluid bed coating were found to be Blower, Temperature and Atomization. These three parameters were incorporated in three level, Planck-Burman Factorial design. Planck-Burman Factorial Design well suited to the goal of optimization. The software developed a 12 run which included 8 combinations of the factors plus four center points used to estimate pure error. A common blend was used to coat 12 batches in a fluid bed coater with a Wurster insert.[27]

Table: Three Level PlanckettBurman Factorial Design.

RUN	BLOWER	TEMPERATURE	ATM AIR
1	30	45	0.8
2	30	45	1.2
3	40	45	0.8
4	30	60	1.2
5	40	60	1.2
6	40	45	1.2
7	40	60	0.8
8	30	60	0.8
9	30	45	0.8
10	40	60	0.8
11	40	45	0.8
12	30	60	1.2

Shows Steps of Coating.

Optimization of Batch Size:[29,30]

Fluidization is affected by the quantity of particles which are introduced into the coating chamber, at least 50% of the volume external to the partition or the wurster tube must be occupied by particles to be coated. This makes it possible to have a sufficient quantity of particles inside the partition to accumulate the maximum coating solution droplets and to avoid thereafter the phenomenon of premature drying or depositing on the walls of partition. To calculate the load of particles to be introduced, it is enough to calculate the external total volume of the partition, to multiply it by the density of the particles in bulk which gives the total capacity in Kg as described in the equation:

$$M = (r_1^2 - r_2^2) \pi L \rho_p$$

Where r_1 and r_2 are, respectively, the chamber radius and partition radius, L is the length of partition, ρ_p is bulk density of pellets. [22]

Optimization of Coating Solution:[31,32]

Strength of coating solution plays an important role in nozzle blockade; Upon increasing the strength of coating solution, the nozzle of Wurster column get blocked due to higher viscosity hence it should not be highly concentrated as well as very much diluted. So it is important to optimize the strength of coating solution. Different concentrations of Coating solutions were used to coat the pellets and efficiency of coating is observed.

Optimization of Spray Rate:[33,34]

Spray rate was determined by the drying capacity of the equipment which is directly proportional to crosssectional area of the air distribution plate rather than by the increase in batch size. At a given atomization pressure and air flow volume, change in liquid spray rate directly affects droplet size which in turn impacts particle agglomeration and may cause lumping. Pellets were fluidized and allowed to coat at different spray rate (rpm) and results were monitored.

Innovations in Fluidized Bed Systems :[18]

Top Spray Granulator

The top spray granulator agglomerates finer particles into larger, free flowing granulates in a one-pot process. Ingredients are mixed and preheated by an upward flow of heated air. Granulation occurs by spraying liquid into the fluidized powder. The granules are subsequently dried with heated air. The top spray granulator can also be used for top spray coating, layering from liquids, and instantizing.

Special features

- One pot process
- Selection of air distributors

Spray Dryer Granulator :

The spray dryer granulator transforms suspensions or solutions into dry, free-flowing, dustless granules. A suspension or solution of the substance to be dried is sprayed onto warm air, simultaneously drying and agglomerating the product. Batch or continuous discharge is available – in the continuous mode, the product is discharged at a controlled rate to maintain an optimum bed height.

Special features

- Compact unit
- Easy scale-up
- Batch or continuous discharge

Top Spray Granulator

Spray Dryer Granulator

Precision-Granulator:[18]

A rotating high velocity air stream is established in the central agglomeration tube. Particles are picked up at the base of the tube and accelerated by the air stream. The particles come into contact with liquid droplets produced from the spray nozzle at the base of the tube \ the relative velocity of air, liquid droplets and particles are high so wetting is efficient and drying begins almost immediately. Most of the feed material is in the outer “holding area”, where the gas velocity is very low. Attrition is greatly reduced. The gas humidity is also low in the holding area so the material is dry not sticky. Individual particles may make repeated cycles (typically from 10 to 1,000) through the tube, allowing very large agglomerates to be built up.

Precision-Coater:

Used for smaller particles, such as powders, granules, seeds, crystals, pellets, and small tablets. The product is coated and partially dried by being blown upward through a central column with atomized liquid and drying air. The material falls into the outer part of the container where heated air completes the drying process. On reaching the air distributor at the base of the module, the product flows again into the central column for further coating. This process continues until the specified degree of coating is obtained.

Special features

- High spray rates for short processes
- Highly controlled product movement
- Minimal agglomeration or granulation

Precision-Granulator

Precision-Coater

Multi Function Fluid-Bed Granulator and Coater :

Vanguard's VPL Series Fluid Bed Granulators and Coaters have multi-functional systems. The top spray system is the third generation of the top spray granulator. It is more efficient than most common fluid bed granulators in the industry. This type of advanced series equipment integrates three fluid bed processes including the top-spray granulating, bottom spray coating, and tangent spray pelleting and coating such that it achieves both economical and technological advantages in solid dose processing and other applications.

Features:

- High efficient dryer
- Granulator meeting different requirement
- Bottom spray coating system
- Tangent spray rotor system for powder layering, pelleting, coating
- Intelligent control system
- 2 bar shock resistant as standard

Advantages, Disadvantages and Applications of Fluidized Bed Systems :[18]

Advantages

- 1) Liquid like behavior, easy to control
- 2) Rapid mixing, uniform temperature and concentrations.
- 3) Resists rapid temperature changes, hence responds slowly to changes in operating conditions and avoids temperature runaway with exothermic reactions.
- 4) Applicable for large or small scale operations.
- 5) Heat and mass transfer rates are high, requiring smaller surfaces.
- 6) Continuous operation.
- 7) Ease of process control due to stable conditions.

Disadvantages

- 1) Bubbling beds of fine particles are difficult to predict and are less efficient.
- 2) Particle comminution (breakup) is common.
- 3) Pipe and vessel walls erode due to collisions by particles.
- 4) Non-uniform flow patterns (difficult to predict).
- 5) Size and type of particles, which can be handled by this technique, are limited.
- 6) Due to the complexity of fluidized bed behavior, there are often difficulties in attempting to scale-up from smaller scale to industrial units.

Applications :[18]

1. Degree of application decides importance of process. Fluid bed systems are widely applied in non- pharmaceutical fields in comparison to their use in pharmaceutical fields as there are numerous apparatus, process and product parameters that affect the quality of final
2. Pharmaceutical product. Also in pharmaceutical field each formulation presents its own individual development problems that had led to fluidized systems not reaching its full potential in pharmaceutical production:
3. Fluidized bed dryers are used in drying of various materials such as powders, tablets, granules, coals, fertilizers, plastic materials.
4. This process is being used in granulation of pharmaceutical powders.
5. Fluidized bed coaters are used widely for coating of powders, granules, tablets, pellets, beads held in suspension by column of air.
6. The three types (Top spray, Bottom spray, Tangential spray) are mainly used for aqueous or organic solvent-based polymer film coatings.
7. Top-spray fluidized bed coating is used for taste masking, enteric release and barrier films on particles/tablets. Bottom spray coating is used for sustained release and enteric release and Tangential spray coating is used for SR and enteric coating products.

CONCLUSION

Fluid bed processor offer unique opportunity to develop and produce coated controlled release products.

However, various process parameters easily can alter the performance of a product and hence should be examined Thoroughly. The interactions of various process parameters presents a great challenge in optimizing the coating process, hence it is important to investigate and understand these variables to ensure a reproducible performance of controlled release products. From the result of this "QRM Three level, Plancklet Burman Design": It has been proved that QRM, along with DoE can be a systematic process for the "assessment, control, communication, and review of any process-related risks to the quality of the drug product." In FBP, there are so many factors which may affect final product. In this study all these parameters were identified and optimized.

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